

KEY INDICATORS

With 95,701 hectares, Ireland had 2.1% of its farmland under organic management, constituting one of the lowest organic area shares in the European Union. Organic farmland trebled between 2001-2022, thus growing slower than the EU average. Regarding organic retail sales, with 166 million euros, an estimated 2.7% of food retail sales were organic in Ireland, thus below the EU organic share.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

30,017 (0.7%)

95,701 ha (2.1%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

219%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

2,606 ha (0.2%)

11,416 ha (2.6%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

121 ha (6.4%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

27,410 ha (0.9%)

84,164 ha (2.1%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

34,366 † (97.9%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

918 (0.7%)

2,193 (1.7%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

60

Processors

88

194

Importers

N/D

144

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

25 M €

166.2 M€ (2.7%)

Per Capita Consumption

6.5 €

33.3 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

840 %

Imports

N/D

55,918 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN IRELAND

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on Eurostat, Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC SALES IN IRELAND

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Bord Bia and other national data sources

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Ireland CAP strategic plan projects a 4-5 fold increase in organic area and more than 10 times the annual expenditure by 2027 compared with 2018. This substantial increase in expenditure is due in part to a trebling of payment rates per hectare for horticulture and permanent crops, and 25-75% increase in support for arable and grassland. These large increases in support have contributed to a sharp rise in the number of producers converting in 2022 and 2023.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	72 kha	337 kha (+368%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	1.6%	7.5% (+368%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	8 M€	89 M€ (+1016%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	111 €	265 € (+139%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	256 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	1,483 M€	7.9%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,757 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	9,832 M€	2.6%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	220	260	300	300
	2023	P2	350	320	800	800
Change from 2019 to 2023			+59%	+23%	+167%	+167%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	170	170	200	200
	2023	P2	300	270	600	600
Change from 2019 to 2023			+76%	+59%	+200%	+200%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+29%	+53%	+50%	+50%
	2023		+17%	+19%	+33%	+33%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The current OAP is Ireland's third since 2008. It is different from most other national OAPs in terms of its focus on individual sub-sectors like milk, meat, arable crops and horticulture. The previous plan was more modest in terms of ambition, both in terms of targets and scope of individual actions. The implementation of the current plan is taking account of the need to respond with information and market to support to the increased rates of conversion stimulated by the higher support payments from 2023.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2013-15	Unspecified increase	N/D
Current Action Plan	2019-25	10% of UAA by 2030 target set in 2023	Individual sector (dairy, beef, arable etc.) targets

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2013 - 2015)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2019 - 2025)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Ireland is almost 50%, making Ireland the lead country in Europe. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids, increased competitiveness, research, innovation and knowledge transfer, and high production and certification standards. Addressing regulatory issues for organic aquaculture also featured in the previous national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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